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POSTNATAL HEALTH CARE PRACTICES AMONG SLUM WOMEN IN UDUMALPET TALUK OF TIRUPUR DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU

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Abstract

The utilization of maternal care services, varies between countries and with in a country. Utilization of maternal care services among pregnant women in slum areas influenced by various factors such as low-income, age, education, medical insurance, clinical risk factors and supply of health care but above all every society has its own traditional beliefs and practices related to pregnancy and health care. Beliefs in super natural power that is holy rituals, salvation offerings and sacrifices are applied at the different stages of life from birth to death. There are many such practices, rituals, beliefs and offerings which either protect or harm the health of the mother and the new born.

Culture influences the way people expectations, and their behaviour in response to certain situations providing culturally competent nursing care means that care is planned and implemented in a way that is sensitive to the needs of individuals, families and groups from diverse cultural populations within the society. Postpartum maternal health care influences the health of both the mothers and their children greatly. The primary objective of the study is to assess the postnatal health care practices of slum women in Udumalpet Taluk.

Key Words: *Postnatal care services, Utilization, slum women, Traditional practices.*

Introduction:

Pregnancy and motherhood are natural processes in the lives of women of reproductive age. These processes are generally considered to be positive and fulfilling experiences. However, for various reasons many women end up dying during pregnancy, childbirth and the post-partum period. Improving maternal health and reducing maternal mortality are accepted as human rights challenges and these issues have been prioritized in several international declarations and

national policies. Improved scientific knowledge and the availability of modern technology have brought several significant successes in global health over the past five decades but maternal mortality reduction remains a serious challenge in the majority of low- and middle-income countries.

India has a huge toll of maternal deaths, with 50,000 deaths in 2013, which constituted 17% of the global burden of maternal mortality. It has achieved a significant decline in the maternal mortality ratio (MMR) from 892 maternal deaths/100,000 live births in 1972–76 to 178 in 2010–12. Nevertheless, the country is still far away from reducing it to 109 maternal deaths per 100,000 live births, which is the millennium development goal (MDG) target for the country.

India is still struggling with a high maternal mortality and morbidity compounded by low utilization of services. Presumably, there are socio-economic and demographic factors, which may play a role in the utilization of maternal health care services. According to a national survey, only 18.8% of pregnant women in India had full antenatal care, which includes at least three visits for antenatal check-up, one tetanus toxoid (TT) injection received and 100 iron and folic acid (IFA) tablets or adequate amount of syrup consumed. Less than half of the respondents had an institutional delivery (47%) and postnatal checkup within two weeks of delivery (49.7%). The figures were even lower in slum areas reflecting non-acceptance or poor utilization/underutilization of maternal health care services in these areas.

The utilization of maternal care services varies between countries with a great underutilization among pregnant women in low-income countries, which may be due to many factors such as age, education, medical insurance, clinical risk factors and supply of health care (e.g., clinic availability, distance to facility).

Every society has its own traditional beliefs and practices related to pregnancy and health care. Beliefs in super natural power that is holy rituals, salvation offerings and sacrifices are applied at the different stages of life from birth to death. There are many such practices, rituals, beliefs and offerings which either protect or harm the health of the mother and foetus in utero. Culture influences the way people expectations, and their behaviour in response to certain situations providing culturally competent nursing care means that care is planned and implemented in a way that is sensitive to the needs of individuals, families and groups from diverse cultural populations within society. Postpartum maternal health care influences the health of both the mothers and their children greatly. Like prenatal care, the postpartum health care that is typically provided during the six-week period after childbirth is very important to the mothers' health.

Objective

The primary objective of the study is to assess the postnatal health care practices of slum women in Udumalpet Taluk of Tirupur District, Tamil Nadu. Specifically, the study aims to estimate that a woman of childbearing age would utilize maternal health care taking into consideration its socio-demographic characteristics.

Materials and methods

Research approach: Descriptive survey research approach.

Research design: Descriptive designs are designed to gain more information about characteristics within a particular field of study.

Sample/Sampling techniques: The purposive sampling technique was adopted to select 200 postnatal mothers.

Instrument/Method of data collection: The interview schedule was used to collect the data 1) Demographic Proforma consists of 7 items which includes age, education, religion, occupation, income, the type of family, and type of residence and 2) structured questionnaire of cultural practices consists of 40 items divided into five sections like Diet, Bath, Spiritual activity, Breast feeding and Baby care.

Analysis: The data was analysed using SPSS version 16.0. Results were tabulated. Statistical Analysis: Frequency distribution and percentage was used for analysis of the result.

Results:

Analysis of base line characteristic of subjects revealed that among multiparous postnatal mothers 49% belongs to the age group of 25-29 years, 48.5% of the mothers were having Primary education, 49.5% of the mothers were belongs to Muslim religion, 89% of the participants were homemakers, 65.5% of the mothers belongs to nuclear family.

Table 1; Distribution of Samples According To Demographic Characteristics N=200

Demographic Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
20-24	29	14.5
25-29	98	49.0
30-34	61	30.5
35-39	12	6.0

Education		
No formal education	8	4.0
Primary	97	48.5
SSLC	56	28.0
HSSLC	28	14.0
Degree & above	11	5.5
Religion		
Hindu	28	14.0
Christian	99	49.5
Muslim	73	36.5
Occupation		
Home maker	178	89.0
Private employee	22	11.0
Income in Rupees		
3001-5000	24	12.0
5001-7000	68	34.0
7001-10000	87	43.5
>10000	28	14.0
Type of Family		
Joint	69	34.5
Nuclear	131	65.5
Type of Resident		
Tiled	152	76
Terraced	48	24

The item wise distribution of sample according to the cultural practices (diet, bath, spiritual activity, breast feed and baby care) described under different headings.

Diet: The present study shows that, in dietary practices during postnatal period, only few (28%) of the postnatal mothers consumed green leafy vegetables to prevent cold to mother and the baby too. 80.50% of the mothers had practice of drinking kalijira kashayam and 79.5% of the mothers consumed special food (home medicine) to increase breast milk and strengthen the bones and muscles during postnatal period. This food is highly nutritious, contains more of ghee, methi and garlic, which helps to increase the breast milk.

Bath: During the post partum period 52.5% of the mothers were restricted to oil massage before hot water bath for 40 days and 56% of the postnatal mothers were restricted from using cold water for washing hands, taking bath, toilet use and drinking purpose.

Spiritual Activities: Majority (84.5%) of the postnatal mothers were restricted to spiritual activities and 87.5% mothers had performed purification ceremony. However, the 65% of people were practicing to keep metal and broom stick under the bed.

Baby Care: In order to prevent/reduce the cold to the baby, 64% of the postnatal mothers were including the herbs in baby bath. 16.5% of the postnatal mothers have applied the herbal medicine to the cord. However 62% of the postnatal mothers had practiced to dispose the dried cord by burial method. The investigator found that the practice of disposal of dried cord by postnatal mothers in Muslim religion, by 14th day with few hairs of the baby, along with a coin will be kept on the coconut tree or put into the stream of water.

The very beginning of the postpartum days the breast milk production will be insufficient. In order to improve the bowel movement of the baby, the postnatal mothers were practicing to give hot water to the baby. The present study showed that 20% of the mothers had practiced to give hot water to the baby. 38% of the mothers had practiced to give home medicine (includes garlic, ginger, pepper and shoot of some selected plants) to the baby to relieve the abdominal discomfort. Application of kajal and use of black thread practice was 99% of the mothers had followed after the naming/purification ceremony to prevent bad eyes. Even though the urine is a source of infection to the baby, 59.5% of the mothers were following unhygienic practice that using a cloth soaked in baby's urine to remove the coated tongue. Although the smoke is not good for health, the 79% of the mothers were had practice of exposing the baby to the dhoopam smoke after bath to protect the baby from evil spirit.

Comparison of cultural practices of postnatal mothers with selected demographic variables.

Age: The major findings identified during the Comparison of the cultural practices with age showed that, 100% of the postnatal mothers with all age groups had a practice of consumption of warm food after delivery whereas 95% of the postnatal mothers of the age group of 30-34 years practiced to drink kalijira (black cumin seed) kashayam for first 3 days after delivery. About 58% of the postnatal mothers of age group of 35-39 years were restricted to drink more water. 89% of the postnatal mothers with age group of 30-34 years had a practice of consuming special food (home prepared) to increase the lactation and strengthen the bones and muscles.

Comparing the cultural practices regarding spiritual activity with different age group revealed that, 96% of the postnatal mothers (20-24 years) were restricted to perform spiritual activities before 40 days, 70% of the postnatal mothers (30-34 years) had a practice of keeping metal and broom stick under the bed. Thirty three percent of the mothers (35-39 years) applied some home medicine to the cord to dry faster, 67% of the postnatal mothers (35-39 years) disposed the cord by burial method. Hundred percent of the postnatal mothers with all the age

group practiced the application of Kajal on the baby's face and use of black thread to prevent bad eye after the purification ceremony. 100% of the mothers with an age group 25-29 years practiced to remove coated tongue by using a cloth soaked in baby's urine.

Education: During the comparison of the cultural practices of postnatal mothers with the education, the researcher found that, 100% of the mothers with all the categories of education practiced to consume warm food, 99% of the mothers with primary education drank Kalijira (black cumin-seed) for first 3 days. 84% of the mothers with secondary education consumed special food (home preparation) to increase the lactation and strengthen the bones and muscles.

Hundred percent of the postnatal mothers with no formal education were restricted to perform spiritual activities before 40 days, 71% of the mothers with PUC practiced to keep the metal and broom stick under the bed.

Hundred percent of the mothers with educational qualification of degree & above fed the (colostrums) first milk, 74% of the mothers with primary education buried the cord when it dries and falls. With all the categories of education mothers practiced to apply Kajal on the baby's face and also of tying black thread to prevent bad eye after the purification ceremony. The majority (88%) of mothers with no formal education practiced to remove coated tongue by using a cloth soaked in baby's urine.

Religion: There were significant differences observed in comparison of the cultural practices with the religion that, 100% of the mothers practiced the consumption of warm food after delivery. Majority (97%) of the Hindu postnatal mothers practiced to drink Kalijira kashayam (black cumin seed) for first 3 days. 58% of the Hindus were restricted to drink more water. 92% of the Hindus were consumed special food (home preparation) to increase the lactation and strengthen bones and muscles.

Ninety eight percentages of the Muslim postnatal mothers were restricted to perform spiritual activities before 40 days. Majority (95%) of the Hindu mothers practiced to keep the metal and broom stick under the bed. 18% of the

Muslim mothers were applied home medicine and herbal oil to the cord to dry faster. All the religion mothers (100%) were practicing to apply Kajal on the baby's face to prevent bad eye after the purification. 67% of the Muslim mothers were practicing to remove coated tongue by using a cloth soaked in baby's urine.

Occupation: The result of comparison of the cultural practices during postnatal period with the occupation showed that, 100% of the mothers practiced to consume warm food. The majority (96%) of the home makers were drinking Kalijira (black cumin-seed) for first 3 days, 47% were restricted to drink more water, 81% were consuming special food (home medicine) to increase lactation and to strengthen the bones and muscles, 91% were restricted to perform spiritual

activities, 66% were keeping metal and broom stick under the bed to prevent evil spirit and 66% have buried the cord when it dries and falls during the postnatal period.

Hundred percent of the private employees applied Kajal on the baby's face and tied black thread around the waist to prevent bad eye. 64% of the home makers removed coated tongue by using a cloth soaked in baby's urine.

Family: The findings of the cultural practices compared with different types of families showed that, the majority (95%) of the mothers from joint family were drinking Kalijira (black cumin-seed) for first 3 days. 47% of the mothers from the joint family were restricted to drink more water. 84% of the mothers from nuclear family practiced to consume special food (home preparation) to increase lactation and to strengthen the bones and muscles.

Ninety one percent of the mothers from joint family were restricted to perform spiritual activities. Majority (93%) of the mothers from nuclear family were practiced to keep metal and broom stick under the bed, 64% of the mothers from the nuclear family have applied home medicine to the cord dry faster. 66% of the mothers from joint family had a practice of burial the cord. The majority (99%) of the mothers from nuclear family were practicing to expose the baby to the dhoopam smoke after the bath.

The 100% of the mothers from nuclear family practiced to apply Kajal on the baby's face and tied black thread to prevent bad eye and also practiced to remove the coated tongue by using a cloth soaked in baby's urine.

Area of residence: The comparison of cultural practices with area of residence showed that, 100% of rural and urban postnatal mothers were practicing the consumption of warm food after delivery. Majority (95%) of the rural mothers were practicing to drink Kalijira (black cuminseed) for first 3 days, 46% of the rural mothers were restricted to drink more water. Majority (87%) of the urban mothers consumed special food (home preparation) for increased lactation and to strengthen the bones and muscles.

The 73% of the urban mothers practiced oil massage before bath during postnatal period. The majorities (96%) of the rural mothers were restricted to perform spiritual activities, 66% were practiced to keep metal and broom stick under the bed, 15% were applied home medicine to the cord to dry faster and 68% were buried the cord when it dries and falls. The 100% of the urban mothers applied Kajal and tied black thread to the baby for prevention of bad eye. The majority (68%) of the rural mothers practiced to remove the coated tongue by using a cloth soaked in baby's urine.

Discussion:

he findings of the study were discussed under following sections;

Section-A: classification of demographic variables

Section-B: assessment of cultural practices of postnatal mothers.

Section-C: comparison of cultural practices with the demographical variables.

Section-1: classification of demographic variables is as follows;

- Analysis of base line characteristic of subjects revealed that the 49% of postnatal mothers were belongs to the age group of 25-29 years.
- Majority (48.5%) of the mothers were having Primary education.
- Most (49.5%) of the mothers were belongs to Muslim religion.
- Referring to the occupation the majority (89%) of the participants were home makers.
- The highest percentage (43.5%) of the mothers had monthly income of Rs.7001-10000.
- Majority (65.5%) of the mothers were from nuclear family.
- Majority (76.0%) of the participants were residing at tiled house.

Section – B: assessment of cultural practices of postnatal mothers.

- All the (100%) postnatal women were consuming hot food after delivery.
- Majority (79.5%) of the mothers consumed special food (home preparation) to increase lactation and to strengthen the bones and muscles.
- Most of the postnatal mothers (98.5%) were restricted to regular hot water bath up to 40 days.
- Majority (87.5%) of the mothers have followed the purification ceremony.
- Majority (99%) of the mothers applied the kajal and black thread to the baby after the purification ceremony to prevent bad eye.

Section-C: comparison of cultural practices with the demographical variables;

- Comparing the cultural practices with the age revealed that the highest percentage of practices were followed by the age group of 35-39 years
- The researcher found that during the comparison with the educational status, the mothers with no formal education and degree & above had followed highest percentage of cultural practices during postnatal period.
- The mothers from Hindu religion followed highest percentage of cultural practices in postnatal period.
- The home makers were giving more importance to the cultural practices of postnatal mother.
- The highest percentage of the mothers from nuclear family were followed the cultural practices.
- Majority of the rural postnatal mothers were following the cultural practices

Conclusion:

Generally, women and their newborn are secluded from the rest of the household to limit contamination from the polluting powers of 'after-birth'. This is widely practiced across India, and is an intrinsic part of women's daily lives in traditional societies. Health professionals should be aware of the patient's culture and which traditional belief complements professional care. Healthcare providers should also advice and educate women about and importance of adhering to the standard practice of postpartum care while outlining appropriate strategies for integration of mother's traditional beliefs and modern approaches of postpartum care.

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